

A Retrospective, Interventional Study to Compare the Efficacy of Letrozole 5 Mg and Letrozole 7.5 Mg in Anovulatory Infertile Patients**Rashi Misra¹, Vasavi Prameela Mummana², Suma B³, Neelam Misra⁴**^{1,4} Director Shivani Hospital and IVF, Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh, India^{2,3} FNB Reproductive Medicine Shivani Hospital and IVF, Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Objective:** To compare the efficacy of letrozole 5 mg and letrozole 7.5 mg in anovulatory infertile patients.**Methods:** A retrospective, an open label interventional, single center study. Total 50 women were divided into two groups of 25 each. 1st group is of Letrozole 5 mg with or without Gonadotropins and 2nd group is of Letrozole 7.5 mg with or without Gonadotropins who have previous unsuccessful ovulation with 2.5 mg of Letrozole. Study participants are of age 22 to 39 years. Study began in Feb 2022 and was completed in November 2022.**Results:** The main objective of successful ovulation is achieved in 44 out of 50 (88.00%). In women who received 5 mg Letrozole, ovulation rate was (21/25) [84.00%] (P-value= <0.05) and pregnancy rates (2/25) [8.00%] (P-value= <0.05). In the subsequent group of 7.5 mg of Letrozole out of 25 patients 23 patients has achieved ovulation (23/25) [92.00%] (P-value= <0.05) and successful pregnancy outcome (9/25) [36.00%]. Overall, with 7.5 mg Letrozole group has higher success ratio in term of Ovulation rate and successful pregnancy outcome. Another key observation was in 5mg group almost 92% patients required HP-hMG administration while in 7.5 mg group only 24% required HP-HMG intervention and multi-follicular development was observed in Letrozole 7.5 mg group. There was no any single case of Ovarian hyperstimulation syndrome (OHSS) in any of the group.**Conclusion:** In this study, we observed that high dose of Letrozole (5 mg or 7.5 mg) associated with higher ovulation rate and successful pregnancy outcome.**Keywords:** ovarian hyperstimulation syndrome (OHSS), Letrozole (LTZ), Polycystic Ovarian Syndrome (PCOS), Follicle- Stimulating Hormone (FSH).This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Letrozole is an oral, potent, reversible, and highly selective aromatase inhibitor with proven first line treatment choice for ovulation induction. Letrozole has a short half-life (45 hours), hence is rapidly eliminated from the body. No adverse effects seen on E target tissues with Letrozole; furthermore, it does not downregulate the estrogen receptor compared to Clomiphene citrate. [1]

Letrozole (LTZ), the prominent drug in the aromatase inhibitor (AI) family, has been introduced as a new choice for ovulation induction in the past decade, especially in polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS) patients who have failed to respond to CC. LTZ also seems to be very efficient in pregnancy rates, equivalent to injectable gonadotropins, at lower cost and with fewer adverse effects. Furthermore, there are extra advantages for LTZ-therapy in comparison to CC, including: normal negative feedback mechanism for follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) in the brain, more mono-follicular cycles, no negative antiestrogenic effects on the endometrial and cervical mucus, lower risk of ovarian hyperstimulation syndrome (OHSS),

and lesser need for cycle monitoring. Hormonal profile of LTZ cycles in infertility literature is a nowadays matter of challenge. It has been shown that LTZ can induce a marked decrease in plasma concentrations of estradiol (E₂) and estrone, with approximately no effect on other steroidal hormones. [2] No accumulation of androgens, androgen precursors, luteinizing hormone (LH), FSH, thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) or renin was reported in pharmacodynamics studies of LTZ. Many researchers have tried Letrozole for ovulation induction, but the ideal and optimal dose of Letrozole is yet highly questionable and remain to be decided. [3]

Materials and Methods

A retrospective, an open label interventional, single center study. Total 50 women were divided into two groups of 25 each. 1st group is of Letrozole 5 mg with or without Gonadotropins and 2nd group is of Letrozole 7.5 mg with or without Gonadotropins who have previous unsuccessful ovulation with 2.5 mg of Letrozole. Study participants are of age 22 to

39 years. Study began in Feb 2022 and was completed in November 2022.

Participants/Materials, Setting, Methods: Total 50 women were selected in 1:1 ratio of 5 mg and 7.5 mg of Letrozole (STIMUCOR Tab) daily from day 2 to day 6 along with Gonadotropins highly purified hMG (HP hMG75150 IU. Gonadotropin intervention was based on follicular delayed response criteria of follicular development on day 8 < 12 mm and estradiol level < 100 pg/ml. The main outcome measure was rate of ovulation and pregnancy.

Main results and the role of chance: The main objective of successful ovulation is achieved in 44 out of

50 (88.00%). In women who received 5 mg Letrozole, ovulation rate was (21/25) [84.00%] (P-value=<0.05) and pregnancy rates (2/25) [8.00%]. In the subsequent group of 7.5 mg of Letrozole out of 25 patients 23 patients has achieved ovulation (23/25) [92.00%] (P-value=<0.05) and successful pregnancy outcome (9/25) [36.00%]. Overall, with 7.5 mg Letrozole group has higher success ratio in term of Ovulation rate and successful pregnancy outcome

Observation chart

Basic and demographic characteristics in study groups

Variable	Treatment group		P value	
	LIT 5	LIT 7.5		
Age (Y)	25.3± 4.4	25.6± 3.5	0.777	
BMI (kg/m ²)	27.0± 3.8	26.4± 4.81	0.674	
Types of infertility	Primary	31 (91.2%)	34 (97.1%)	0.356
	Secondary	3 (8.8%)	1 (2.9%)	
Pattern of ovary	PCOS	24 (68.6%)	23 (65.7%)	1
	non-PCOS	11 (31.4%)	12 (34.3%)	
Familial history of PCOS	Yes	1 (2.9%)	3 (8.6%)	0.614
	No	34 (97.1%)	32 (91.4%)	
LH /FSH (mIU/ml)	1.35± 2.43	1.94± 1.91	0.082	
TSH (µu/ml)	2.95± 3.03	3.29± 4.17	0.376 ^a	
PRL (ng/ml)	24.5± 41.38	29.2± 65.43	0.672 ^a	
The number of previous treatment cycles	1.09± 0.39	1.25± 0.52	0.096 ^a	

Results

The main objective of successful ovulation is achieved in 44 out of 50 (88.00%). In women who received 5 mg Letrozole, ovulation rate was (21/25) [84.00%] (P-value=<0.05) and pregnancy rates (2/25) [8.00%] (P-value=<0.05). In the subsequent group of 7.5 mg of Letrozole out of 25 patients 23 patients has achieved ovulation (23/25) [92.00%] (P-value=<0.05) and successful pregnancy outcome (9/25) [36.00%]. Overall, with 7.5 mg Letrozole group has higher success ratio in term of Ovulation rate and successful pregnancy outcome. Another key observation was in 5mg group almost 92% patients required HP-hMG administration while in 7.5 mg group only 24% required HP-HMG intervention and multi-follicular development was observed in Letrozole 7.5 mg group. There was no any single case of Ovarian hyperstimulation syndrome (OHSS) in any of the group.

Statistical Analysis: The collected data was summarized by using frequency, percentage, mean & S.D. To compare the qualitative outcome measures Chi-square test or Fisher's exact test was used. To compare the quantitative outcome measures independent t test was used. If data was not following normal distribution, Mann Whitney U test was used. SPSS version 22 software was used to

analyze the collected data. p value of <0.05 was statistically significant.

Discussion

A systematic review and meta-analysis was done by Liu A et al. The objective of this study was to investigate and compare the effectiveness of letrozole and clomiphene citrate for improving fertility outcomes, including pregnancy rate, miscarriage rate, multiple pregnancy rate, and incidence rate of adverse events, number of dominant follicles, endometrial thickness at hCG day and serum E2 on hCG day. The results of this study conclude that letrozole is as effective as clomiphene in women with unexplained infertility. [4] Letrozole at a dose of 2.5 mg seems more effective. Further high-quality studies assessing the possible effectiveness of letrozole in selected groups of patients are warranted.

Roy et al did a prospective randomized trial comparing the efficacy of letrozole and clomiphene citrate in induction of ovulation in polycystic ovarian syndrome. Number of ovulatory cycle in letrozole group was 196 (66.6%) versus 216 (67.9%) in CC group (P=0.712). The mean mid-cycle endometrial thickness was 9.1±0.3 mm in letrozole group and 6.3±1.1 in CC group, which was statistically significant (P=0.014). The mean estradiol [E2] level in clomiphene citrate group was

significantly higher in CC group (364.2±71.4 pg/mL) than letrozole group (248.2± 42.2 pg/mL). 43 patients from the letrozole group (43.8%) and 28 patients from the CC group (26.4%) became pregnant. They concluded that Letrozole and CC have comparable ovulation rate. The effect of letrozole showed a better endometrial response and pregnancy rate compared with CC. [5]

In a study very similar to our 's, Wang HY et al did a comparison of the efficacy of two doses of letrozole alone or with continuous recombinant follicle-stimulating hormone for ovulation induction in anovulatory women. The number of follicles, endometrial thickness and serum estradiol levels were significantly higher in the letrozole + rFSH groups than in the letrozole-alone groups ($p < 0.05$), but no significant difference was found between the two doses of letrozole, whether alone or with rFSH. Treatment with letrozole + rFSH was more efficacious than letrozole alone for pregnancy in the IUI program; however, the effect of 5.0 mg/day of letrozole versus 2.5 mg/day of letrozole on ovulation was equivalent, regardless of whether rFSH was used.

Ramezanzadeh F et al did a randomized trial of ovulation induction with two different doses of letrozole in women with PCOS. Patients were randomly divided into two groups and treated with either 5 mg/day (30 patients, group 1) or 7.5 mg/day (37 patients, group 2) Letrozole for 5 days starting from day 3 of the menstrual cycle. When the leading follicle reached 18 mm in diameter, ovulation was triggered by an injection of HCG and timed intercourse was advised thereafter. The primary outcome measures were the number of follicles and days to reach mature follicle and the secondary endpoints were endometrial thickness, day 7 testosterone level, ovulation and pregnancy rates. The pregnancy rate per first ovulatory cycle was 25.8% in group 1 and 21.2% in group 2 without significant difference. The results of this study did not show any advantage to the use of 7.5 mg/day over 5 mg/day dose of Letrozole as the first line treatment for induction of ovulation in women with PCOS.

Ghomian N et al did a randomized clinical trial on comparing the cycle characteristics of two different initiation days of letrozole treatment in clomiphene citrate resistant PCOS patients in IUI cycles. The aim of this study was to compare the ultrasonographic and hormonal characteristics of two different initiation times of LTZ in clomiphene citrate (CC) failure patients and to study androgen dynamics during the cycle. Hormonal profile and ultrasonographic scanning were done on cycle day 3 and three days after completion of LTZ treatment (cycle day 10 or 12). The cycle characteristics, the ovulation and pregnancy rate were compared between two groups. To conclude LTZ is an

effective treatment in CC failure PCOS patients. There are no significant differences regarding ovulation and pregnancy rates between two different protocols of LTZ starting on days 3 and 5 of menstrual cycle.

Conclusion

We observed that high dose of Letrozole (5 mg or 7.5 mg) associated with higher ovulation rate and successful pregnancy outcome. This study reports positive responses elicited by administration of 5mg and 7.5 mg of letrozole in patients with anovulatory response with conventional dose of 2.5 mg.

What we learnt from this study: Despite several studies that have shown the effectiveness of letrozole for ovarian stimulation, there have been very few studies to determine the optimal dose. This study reports positive responses elicited by administration of 5mg and 7.5 mg of letrozole in patients with anovulatory response with conventional dose of 2.5 mg.

Limitations: The limitation of this study was short period of follow-up which cannot detect the teratogenic effects of these drugs if any. While there are advantages in performing a retrospective study, such as decreased costs, the chance of selection bias is increased.

Declarations:

Funding: None **Conflicts of interest/Competing interests:** None **Availability of data and material:** Department of Reproductive Medicine Shivani Hospital and IVF, Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh, India **Code availability:** Not applicable **Consent to participate:** Consent taken **Ethical Consideration:** There are no ethical conflicts related to this study. **Consent for publication:** Consent taken

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